

EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF THE TORSIONAL RESIDUAL STRENGTH AFTER IMPACT OF CFRP TUBES

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SUMMARY

In this paper the residual strength to torsion of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) tubes, of different lay-ups, after a low velocity lateral impact was experimentally measured and compared with the resistance of undamaged tubes in order to develop suitable design criteria.

Keywords: CFRP, Tube, Torsion, Impact, Residual Strength

INTRODUCTION

One of the issues that a designer has to consider in the project of CFRP structures is the residual strength after low velocity and low energy impacts that are very common events in the component's life. In many cases the effects of such impacts on the external ply of the laminate are barely visible, or non visible at all, nevertheless the load bearing capacity of the component could be reduced due to the internal plies delamination in particular as regards the resistance to compression. This problem has been analysed extensively in literature, also by the authors [1]. CFRP tubes have been studied in literature mostly in the cases of internal pressure or axial load, while as regards thin tubes under torsion the research focused on the elastic equilibrium stability.[2] In this paper thick walled tubes loaded in torsion, utilized for example in sailboats winches or high speed shafts in the paper manufacture industry, were considered and their behaviour after a low velocity impact was studied.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Four series of T300-epoxy tubes, whose lay-ups are shown in table 1, were cured in autoclave. Their dimensions were: length 200 mm, inner diameter 50 mm, thickness 2,55 mm..Different test combination have been done by means of a servo-hydraulic machine (see figure 1) with a load capacity exceeding 50 kNm, equipped with a piezoelectric load cell (PCB Piezotronics, Model 208A35) instrumented pendulum. The head of the load cell was spherical with a 12.7 mm diameter.

Table 1: lay-ups and test conditions

CPS	[45/-45] _{4s}	NI	Undamaged
CPNS	[45/-45] ₈	IS	Impact damaged
QIS	[0 ₂ /45/-45/45/-45/90 ₂] _s	IT1	Imp.dam. under torque level 1
QINS	[0 ₂ /45/-45/45/-45/90 ₄ /45/-45/45/-45/0 ₂]	IT2	Imp.dam. under torque level 2

The estimated impact energy was 7 J, corresponding to the one of a small tool falling from an height of one meter, while the velocity was 3,5 m/s. In particular three kind of

Figure 1: Experimental device

test have been done: torsion, torsion after impact, impact on preloaded tubes in torsion at two different load levels followed by the measure of the residual strength. Torque tests were monitored by means of acoustic emission technique.

Figure 2: Residual strength

RESULTS

The results are shown in figure 2, with the symbols of table 1. The ultimate load in torsion is reduced at least by a factor 2 due to impact. The torsional preload, providing energy to the damage process induced by impact, further reduces the residual strength.

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